

**Redefining the Identity issues; Contestations; Autonomy Movement and Politics of
Bodo people in Assam**

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Abstract

The Bodo movement due to the negligence and ignorance by Assam Government is a long-standing ethnic issue in Assam since 1966. The Bodos, known as first settlers in Brahmaputra valley demanding for separate state 'Udayachal' later 'Bodoland' by slogan divide Assam 50/50. As an outcome of prolong movement, the government of India came forward with the BAC (1993), BTC (2003) and BTR (2020) agreements but couldn't satisfy the Bodos aspirations for self-autonomy. The paper deals with the redefining of identity issues that resulted movements, contestations and politics of Bodos in Assam.

Introduction

The nationalists are born out of the feelings of the nationalism. Bodo Nationalists are born because of the realization about their historical past of their identity as a distinct nation. The Bodo movement is a consequence of the realization of their existence as a nation and race that had been threatened. The Bodo tribe were compelled to seek their own identity linguistically, ethnically, culturally and politically (Narzinary 2011, p. 01). The Bodoland movement under the purview of Indian Constitution, though the armed group NDFB were demanding independent country curving out from India. Whatever actions they had undertaken were to seek political sovereignty for their own nation. These can be called separate state or homeland within or over Indian territory.

The Bodos are ethnically Indo-Mongoloid, linguistically Tibeto-Burman family were inhabitants of South East-Asia and west China were migrated to Brahmaputra valley during 5000 BCE. Historically they are known as the Ashura, Kirata, Mlecha, Kacharis, now Bodos. The Borok, Deuri, Dimasa, Sonowal, Garo, Rabha, Thengal and Mech are the cognate tribes of same ancestry. They are little known by the outside world because of very less written history and documents. Presently the Bodos are residing in Brahmaputra valley of Assam, Mechi river valley of Nepal, North Bengal and Garo Hills (Dattaray 1989, p. 12).

The ancestors of Bodos earlier ruled entire Kamrupa kingdom known as Mlecha dynasty till their kingdom was conquered by the Pala dynasty. The loss of Kingdom resulted them to get divided into Kachari, Tipperah, Dimasa, Koch, Mech. During British era, the social deprivations, untouchability, negative impacts of assimilation, the critical rules of the develop community, losses of their ancestral lands and the issues of language made them to form a superstructure of various movements since 1966.

The Indian Government, now and then came forward for the solution of Bodo movement by BAC (1993), BTC (2003) and BTR (2020) agreements but couldn't satisfy the Bodos. This paper attempted to give insights of the identity issue, Bodo movement and present situations of identity politics in Bodo region.

Redefining the issues of identity crisis of Bodos

After the arrival of Aryans in Assam, the sense of discrimination and practices of untouchability were somehow started and became prevalent in the region (Narzary 2011, p. 18). The Bodos and cognate tribes were regarded as untouchables by the higher castes. The higher caste never accepted them in their society was the most unsympathetic with their ideals and aspirations.

The participation of Bodos in India's freedom movement brought little consciousness among them about their self-identity and rights particularly in relation to Assamese people (Singh 2002, pp.90-93). Again, the Brahma Somaj preached by Gurudev Kalicharan Brahma in early 20th century influenced to reform the Bodo society. It was a self-revolution movement that witnessed a remarkable spread of socio-religious, educational and political awareness among the Bodos. The formation of Assam Kachari Jubak Sanmilani (1928) was also played a crucial role to integrate with the various cognate tribes of greater 'Kachari' community scattered all over Assam for the efforts to ameliorate their society and emancipate it from the bondage of illiteracy and social backwardness. Despite their understanding about the relevant of Education, the poverty and lack of consciousness remain as obstacles among the tribal people. In these prevailing situations, under the leadership of Kalicharan Brahma, they submitted memorandum to Simon Commission in 1929 (Times of India 2016, p. 01). In the memorandum, they demanded reservation and separate representation for plain tribals in Assam and one reserved seat in central legislature. Demanded free studentship and scholarship to Kachari students in schools-colleges according to their percentage in Assam to encourage their students. They

further asserted, the Kachari community do not recognize themselves as a lower class or untouchable. They are distinct from the Hindu community in all respect socially and religiously.

In the Government of India Act-1935 provisioned for four reserved seats in Assam provincial Assembly. Sri Rupnath Brahma, a prominent Bodo leader became a minister in Bordoloi Ministry in September, 1938. In 1946, Indian National Congress appoints Mr. Dharanidhar Basumatary as a member in Constituent Assembly. But the Assamese people were not about to accept and tolerate for coming possible political adversary from Tribals. There was an apprehension of political leadership may grow among the tribals because of their numerical strengths in Assam. So, Charan Narzary said, *'Right from the beginning they (Assamese) pursued an undeclared anti-tribal policy and had been working actively in a systematic manner to keep the tribals subdued and get them completely assimilated into the Assamese society by obliterating their distinctive ethnic identity.'*

The assimilation may not be harmful but not often beneficial for tribals. In Assam, the assimilation means conversion of a tribal into Assamese Hindu that negatively impacted of loss of identity. The assimilation and categorization of Hindunised Bodo as Assamese in census had reduced the Bodo population in the official record (Memorandum, 1929 p.01).

The Bordoloi Sub-Committee was formed by Constituent Assembly to study the issues in tribal in North-East Frontier (Assam) and Excluded Area. The Sub-committee headed by Gopinath Bordoloi was needed to suggest for necessary constitutional provision to be added in Indian Constitution. But the issues of the tribals of plain area of Assam were left out by this Sub-Committee to be dealt with. The tribals of plain area of Assam neither included in the Fifth nor in Sixth Scheduled area. Charan Narzary said, 'all this happened because of the biased attitude and deep heinous conspiracy by the Assamese leaders to deprive the tribals of plain area from their legitimate due. If they were included either in the Fifth or the Sixth Schedule, they would have undoubtedly enjoyed autonomy to protect their ethnic identity and lands.'

The land issue was also very serious. They had stories from their forefathers about abundant of lands. But they got to see lakh of landless tribals because of Government's failure to protect the tribal lands. The tribal lands are covered by the tribal belt and blocks as per the provisions given by the Chapter X of the Assam Land and Revenue Regulation Act-1886 amended in 1962. The state government notified plain tribes, hill tribes, tea-tribes, Santals as SC and Koch Rajbanshi of Goalpara as backward class and need to be protected because of their primitive

conditions, lack of education and incapability of development (Mahanta 2013, pp. 49-58). But ever since the enactment of this law, its provisions were never implemented. Due to rapid industrialization and urbanization, the tribals have lost their ancestral lands because of lack of land certificates. The Government neither absorb them in new economic set-up nor had taken any scheme for their rehabilitation to save them from crushing impact of urbanization and industrialization. The issues were raised by All Assam Kachari Association, Bodo Chatra Sanmilani and Kachari Jubok Sanmilani several times. Till now, Lakhs of Bodo people are residing in the forest reserve lands without land holding documents.

Again, by the Assam official Language Act-1960, the Assam Government tried to impose Assamese as compulsory official language in every official purpose of Assam. After that the English and Hindi can be used for the official purposes in secretarial and offices of the Assam Government offices (Assam official language Act-1960, p.03). This imposition by Assam government brought new tensions among the all the other communities including Bodos and Bengali.

The Bodo Thunlai Afad (Bodo Sahitya Sabha-BSS) was formed on 16th November, 1952 to work for the upliftment of the Bodo literature and language since its inception. The Sabha not only protested against the act-1960, but also demanded for the establishment of Bodo medium in schools in Roman Script.

These issues with Assam Government, the Bodo and other tribal people believed that the Government had done enough harms to the tribals. Forced assimilation, infiltration of illegal migrants into the tribal lands and misrule by means of oppression were the reasons to destroy the Bodos and other indigenous tribal people of Assam.

In 1967, the Dularay Boro Phoraisa Afad (All Bodo Students Union-ABSU) and PTCA (Plains Tribal Council of Assam) were formed. The PTCA launched political movement and demanded '*separate state Udayachal*' for the plain tribals at the northern valley of Brahmaputra whereas the ABSU were working for the upliftment of the Bodo students. The PTCA campaigned to boycott the Lok Sabha election on 1968 particularly in Kokrajhar constituency. They submitted a memorandum by demanding '*Udayachal*' to the then Prime Minister of India Smt. Indira Gandhi ji, President V.V. Giri ji and to the Home Ministry (Dash 1989, 335-342). This prolongs movement occurs till the North-Eastern Areas (Re-organization) Act-1971. This act was reorganizing the undivided Assam by establishing the Manipur, Tripura, Meghalaya as separate states and the Mizoram and Arunachal Pradesh as union territories. But the '*Udayachal*' demand didn't get enough importance. The PTCA leaders failed to pressure the Government,

instead, they particularly Bodo leaders supported and participated actively the anti-foreigner movement by All Assam Student's Union (AASU).

In 1985, the Assam accord was signed. As per the clause 6th of the Assam accord that provided for the preservation and development of only Assamese language and cultural identity. the Board of Secondary Education Assam (SEBA) by a notification, imposed Assamese as a compulsory language in schools in February 1986.

The tribal interests were bypassed by the clause 6th of the Assam accord. Some Bodo group started to believe that the PTCA leaders didn't pressurize the Government, they assumed that the PTCA leaders after holding selfish political positions; they already surrendered their dreams for separate homeland.

The Dularay Boro Phoraisa Afad and Bodo Thunlai Afad opposed Clause 6 of the Assam Accord, arguing that it might legitimize the imposition of Assamese language and culture on the Bodos (Nath 2003, pp. 533-545). The Bodo and other tribals incensed with this decision of Assam Government. It revoked the Bodo to feel that the chauvinist Assamese again tried to dominate the Bodo and Tribals.

The ABSU and BPAC (Bodo people Action Committee) re-launched fresh movement in a democratic manner to formed separate state Bodoland by curving out from Assam with the slogan 'Divide Assam 50/50' under the leadership of Upendranath Brahma on 2nd March, 1987. Having bitter experience of negligence and repressive rule under the administration, the Bodo people have deep conviction in their heart that only the Bodoland will guarantee to preserve their identity. During that time, Prafulla Kumar Mahanta was Chief Minister in Assam.

The Government responded the movement group by using forces through Assam police, army and other Para military. There was a mass gathering at Guwahati judge field on 12th June, 1987, thousands of movement supporters were participated. After the program, while returning to home, some unidentified miscreants attacked the movement groups at Tihu in Nalbari District resulted a death of a Student Sujeet Narzary. Later, the ABSU movement transformed to violent tactics. The movement supporters started to attacked non-tribals, government officials including schools, markets, railways and bridges.

Similarly, the Boro Security Force (BrSF) later known as National Democratic Front of Boroland (NDFB) was also founded under the leadership of Ranjan Daimary, Gobinda Basumatary, Dharendra Boro on 03rd October, 1986 to fight for independent country 'Boroland'. It was an Armed group that started to conceive more militancy in the hearts of the

Bodo youth as a re-response to government's responses that gradually developed to full bloom. The rise of militancy resulted loss of human lives, human rights violation, threat to human security including fratricidal killings among the Bodos.

The Bodo Agreements

After the sudden death of Upendranath Brahma on 01st May, 1990, Sansuma Khungur Bwiswmuthiary became ABSU President and lead the negotiations with the Governments. The BAC (Bodoland Autonomous Council) was signed by the movement leaders with the Assam and Central Government to end up the tremendous violence in the region on 20th February, 1993.

But the accord was never implemented properly. Because of the confusion and disagreements over the boundary, failure to provide rehabilitation to the surrendered insurgents and confusions of power and functions of the Council, the then CEM of BAC Sansuma Khungur Bwiswmuthiary rejected and resigned from the post.

The then Dularay Boro Phoraisa Afad (ABSU) President Mr. Swmbla Basumatary also denounced the BAC Accord and resubmits new memorandum to Mr. P.V. Narasimha Rao, the then Prime Minister of India on 9th March, 1996 to revive the movement for Bodoland.

The Bodo Liberation Tigers Force (BLTF) for parallel armed struggle was also formed by the leadership of Bir Chilagang and Hagrama Basumatary for the movement of separate state on 18th June, 1996. The armed struggle was gradually become in leading position but it brought ethnic clashes and killing of many people including women and children in the region.

The BLTF declared ceasefire in July 1999. During ceasefire, the Kargil war broke out between India and Pakistan. It was this anti-government militant group which spoke to patronage the Indian government by joining the Indian Army against the Pakistan which impresses the government officials during the negotiations held between the BLTF and the Indian Government making an impetus in the signing of Memorandum of Settlement.

The BTC (Bodoland Territorial Council) agreement had been signed on 10th February, 2003 between BLTF with the Central and State Government. BTC was established under the Sixth Schedule through the Sixth schedule to the Constitution (Amendment) Act-2003. The BTC is

comprising of Kokrajhar, Chirang, Baksa and Udalguri district by total area of 8822 KM.² This BTC jurisdiction will be known as BTAD (Bodoland Territorial Area District). The agreement brought new aspirations for the progress, prosperity and security to the Bodo people politically, socially, culturally and economically through self-governing capacity. The agreement recognized the Bodo language under the 8th Schedule of Indian Constitution also.

The Politics of Identity and Contestation

The BTC is conferred with legislative, executive, administrative and financial powers. It is constituted with 40 elected and 6 nominated members. 30 seats reserved for ST, 5 for non-ST and 5 for general. Total 40 different subjects were transferred to BTC authority. Funds shall be provided by the both State and central government. BTC itself has some revenue from transports, land, natural resources like forests (other than reserved forest), liquor shop tax, lotteries, town committee, sericulture etc. The funds from any sources can be utilized for the developmental works like constructions of road, bridges, hospitals, school buildings, appointments of 3rd and 4th grade, subsidies to poor, establishment of research and development centres for the protections of tribal languages, lands, culture, traditions, customs etc. Since the agreement, Hagrama Mahilary became the Chief of BTC and later formed Bodoland People Front (BPF), a political party.

The NDFB, who were fighting for sovereign country were neutral during agreement, later they termed the agreement as an insult to the Bodo nation. They criticized the new accord has more provisions for the rights of the non-tribals than the tribal people. The agreement allowed land ownership rights to the people all category in the BTAD area. This is the against of the Assam Land Revenue Regulation Act of 1886 as amended in 1964 and 1974, which established tribal belt and blocks to ensure the tribal's exclusive rights over land within these areas in Assam. The BTC accord has legitimized the illegal migrants and the encroachers also to settle down permanently in the region and occupied the tribal's ancestral lands. If the tribals failed to handle absolute right over their ancestral land, the survival of the tribal community with their distinct identity and culture can never be possible. The increase in non-tribal population in Bodo area will marginalize the population structure of the indigenous people in their own land. Some Bodo intellectuals and Student leaders also believed that BTC accord has miserably failed to

reflect the aspirations of the Bodos because of the thousands of Boro people did not sacrifice and suffered for mere economic solution.

The absence Village Council Development Committee (VCDC) election has also developed ill-feeling and division between the Bodo and non-Bodo people. VCDC is the gram panchayat system under Bodoland Territorial council. The council government had been enjoyed such political opportunities simply by selecting or nominating by favoring the Bodos without the conduct of election procedure.

The non-Bodo people were opposing the formation of the BTC by arguing, the 70% of the non-Bodo population cannot be controlled by the 30% Bodo people. The 18 different non-Bodo organizations came together and formed the Sanmilita Janagosthiya Sangram Samiti (Nath 2003, p. 540). Gradually they earned supports from the non-Bodo people in the region and struggled to revoke BTC agreement. Some non-Bodo organizations even threatened to adopt violent means also. These waves of unity among the non-Bodo people brought the result in the Lok Sabha election that the Kokrajhar Lok Sabha Constituency (ST) got occupied by duplicate ST Naba Kumar Sarania for two consecutive terms from 2014 to 2024. Naba Sarania was a ULFA militant who was arrested on 20th August, 2012 for robbery, murder and kidnap was in bail.

It was a great challenge of the BTC government and other Bodo organizations to earn confidence from the non-Bodo communities. The responsibility of the BTC government was to give their assurance of security to the non-Bodo people. The BTC was guaranteed the land rights and equal rights to the non-tribal people with tribals who were living in the region since before the accord. But the National Democratic front of Bodoland (NDFB) never agreed. This disagreement and political awareness among the non-Bodo brought more tension and insecurity. The political differences of Bodo and non-Bodo in the region brought chaos resulted several ethnic violence between Bodo and Muslim in 2012 and Bodo Santali conflict in 2014. The ABSU during the presidentship of Promod Baro was restarted the Bodoland Movement from 2nd March, 2010 with more strength and mass support. They claimed the dreams of the Bodos have not been fulfilled by the BTC because of it has less power and functions to protect the tribal interests. In addition, the ABSU always opposed the gun culture. They always invited the underground organization NDFB to declare cease fire and come to table talk with the

Government for peace and prosperity. The new generation Bodo leaders already familiar with the negative impact of the insurgency and counter insurgency in the region because of many innocent Bodo youth have been killed in fake encounter and got arrested by armed forces in the name of Bodo militant.

The NDFB factions declared ceasefire. The third accord Bodoland Territorial region (BTR) has been signed on 27th February of 2020 with ABSU and all faction of NDFB as the comprehensive and final solution of the demand of Bodo without further division of the Assam. The movement leaders claimed it as the best agreement ever that it will fulfill all the aspirations of the Bodo, the Deputy commissioner shall be under the jurisdiction of the Council Government, direct funding from the Centre, the area of the Council shall be expanded to Gohpur, the constituency shall be increased to 60, the Bodo of the outside BTR shall be given new statutory council, many more educational institutions will be established and more power and functions to be transferred to the council.

After the agreement, the council election was needed to be conducted. But due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the election was postponed and Governor Rule had been imposed on 27th April, 2020.

We see, there is a huge impact of emotions and nationalism to earn vote from the Bodos in elections. The agreement gave new aspirations to the Bodos to attach emotionally with the movement leaders. The movement leaders together formed new party United People Party Liberal (UPPL). We could expect the new party would be gaining absolute majority in election. But due to the delay in election, the people of the region got chance to study the BTR agreement deeply. The insightful understanding of the agreement, dissatisfaction, disagreement and criticism by the of Bodo intellectual impacted in council election. The UPPL party only succeeded to occupy only 12 seats and failed to be in majority. Congress and o-Boro 1 seat each, BJP and BPF occupied 9 and 17 seats respectively. Later, the UPPL formed coalition government with BJP and other independent Candidates.

Conclusion

The Bodoland Territorial Council (BTC) established through the Sixth Schedule to the Constitution (amendment) Act-2003 was very strong enough to secure its geographical

boundary. As per the paragraph 1 and its sub-paragraphs of Sixth Schedule, the Governor has power to include, exclude, increase, diminish or divide the Autonomous areas. It was not applicable to the Bodoland Territorial council (BTC) except by constitutional amendment as per footnotes added in Sixth schedule. But the 3.1(ii) clause of BTR added for the exclusion and inclusion of villages from BTC jurisdiction.

The BTR agreement has not been passed in parliament till writing of this paper. But some clauses possible by the state Government have been implemented instantly. The inclusion of the Bodo language as an associate official language in Assam, establishment of separate Directorate for Bodo medium and other Tribal languages, formation of Bodo Kachari Welfare Autonomous Council (BKWAC), transferred of responsibility of 16 departments of council to the deputy commissioner for monitoring and separate department in state Government to deal with Bodoland Territorial Council.

The third phase Bodo movement was giving ambitions to achieve the separate state Bodoland because of its huge mass supports. The instant BTR agreement seems to fulfill some leader's personal greedy to occupy political power only. So, Sansuma Khungur Bwiswmuthiary, Daorao Dekreb Narzary, Hiracharan Narzinary and likeminded Bodo intellectuals started to criticize the agreement and threatened to revive the movement. They opposed the implementation by arguing, it is going to hamper and scrap the existing structure of the Bodoland Territorial Council-2003 in case of legislative, executive, administrative and financial. The transfer of 16 departments to Deputy Commissioner is a deep-rooted conspiracy of the state government to snatch away the autonomy from the BTC. The provision of the exclusion of the existing area will weaken the strong geographical boundary of the council. They file a petition to the High Court to review some clauses of the BTR agreement.

The reality of the new Bodo accord will be on the hand of the governments. All the Bodo people are happy with the homecoming of the National Democratic front of Boroland (NDFB) cadres. The clause 9.4 of the memorandum was promised that the criminal cases against the NDFB members shall be withdrawn by the government. Bodo intellectuals believed that it would be better if the agreement brought general amnesty for the all-militant cadre who surrendered and disband the organization along with. But this clause 9.4 has not been

implemented yet, some ex NDFB cadres still receives arrest warrants. So, these present situations don't show the end of the Bodo movement. The dissatisfaction of agreement, implementations and governance of present council government are loosening public supports day by day.

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